

Flavivaccine

Project website /D6.5

WP 6, T 6.2

Authors: Sara Lazzarin (ICONS)

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Technical references

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- *PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)
- SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
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Document history

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List of Acronyms

	Definition
PCD	Plan for Communication and Dissemination
D&C	Dissemination and Communication

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Executive Summary

This deliverable completes the Plan for Communication and Dissemination submitted at M6 and focuses on the steps undertaken for the creation of a project website to promote the EU-funded project FLAVIVACCINE.

Activities related to the website have been carried out as follows:

Table 1: Complete summary of website activities

Task	Activities	Timing and notes	KPI DoA
6.2- Communication activities (ICONS)	Visual identity and logo	<i>M2 – delivered</i>	50K visitors on FLAVIVACCINE's website by the end of the project.
	.eu domain acquired	<i>M2 – delivered</i>	
	.com domain acquired	<i>M3 – delivered</i>	
	Drafting text and internal process to review	<i>M3-M4 – delivered</i>	
	Landing graphic design	<i>M3 – delivered</i>	
	Landing Web development	<i>M3 – delivered</i>	
	First release of the website (Landing page)	<i>M5 – delivered M4</i>	
	Second release map finalised	<i>M5 – delivered</i>	
	Drafting text and internal process to review	<i>M5-M6 – ongoing</i>	
	Additional graphic design	<i>M6-M7 – ongoing</i>	
	Update development	<i>M6 – ongoing</i>	
	Second release of the website	<i>Internal deadline set at M8</i>	

1. Introduction to the Website deliverable

The Plan for Communication and Dissemination (PCD - D6.1) serves as the blueprint for the project's communication and dissemination activities, laying the groundwork for the exploitation strategy. It sets out the communication and dissemination (C&D) activities, channels, formats, and materials designed to achieve the desired impact in terms of awareness, acceptance, and support for the uptake of the project's results.

The website is a critical component of this strategy, serving as the main channel for communicating with its audiences, and as the entry point to address the key stakeholders along the vaccine value chain.

It aims **to maximise visibility for the project and raise awareness about its goal** of delivering a safe, cost-effective, and efficient solution to reduce the burden of diseases caused by flaviviruses like dengue, yellow fever, Zika, and West Nile. Additionally, the website aims to **provide public access to relevant results, news items, audio-visual content, and public deliverables.**

Therefore, this **deliverable (D6.5) specifically focuses on the website's development.** It provides information about the website's hosting domain, the process which led to the website's first release (**M4**), and the **steps leading to the second release.** It details the **structure and foreseen sections** of the final FLAVIVACCINE website, and it also addresses **the website's updating** to ensure it remains current with news items, public deliverables, dissemination materials, and events.

2. First release

The first release of the website is the '**landing page**' designed to provide easy access to essential project information. Launched in April 2024 (M4), this page **established FLAVIVACCINE's online presence**. This chapter details the steps taken to launch the landing page.

2.1. Domain

The first step in the realisation of the website was the acquisition of the domains. The FLAVIVACCINE project has secured two different domain names:

- **flavivaccine.eu** domain: Acquired by ICONS in Month 2 (M2), this domain is commonly used by European projects, facilitating easy identification and emphasizing the project's EU dimension.
- **flavivaccine.com** domain: Acquired with input from the project coordinator, IRD, this domain is intended to support exploitation beyond the project's end and to ensure ownership of brand assets.

Currently, the website is hosted on the **flavivaccine.eu** domain, with the **flavivaccine.com** domain redirecting to the .eu site.

2.2. Visual identity

For the FLAVIVACCINE website, this visual identity provides a **unified look and feel** that aligns with the project's branding. The FLAVIVACCINE visual identity was formulated in M1 and finalized in M2 following the work of ICONS' graphic designer, with input from the Communication Team and IRD, the project coordinator.

For further details on how FLAVIVACCINE's visual identity was created, refer to the Plan for Communication and Dissemination (PCD), Deliverable D6.1, section 2.3.

Figure 1: Visual identity of FLAVIVACCINE

Building on this, FLAVIVACCINE has established a **distinctive project logo** and consistent design elements for all project-related materials, and for applications in its channels including the Website.

Figure 2: Application of the visual identity in the project's landing page

All the project C&D products, including the website, must align with this visual identity and indicate that the project received funding from the European Union, featuring the EU emblem. Each publication will include this disclaimer (from **Grant Agreement 17.3**):

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Figure 3: Detail of the landing page showing the EU disclaimer

2.3. Landing page text and the D&C approval process

Simultaneously with the finalisation of the visual identity, efforts began to craft an appropriate text for the initial release of the website, considering the concerns of project partners and the coordinator about inadvertently disseminating confidential information. To address these concerns, a **process for publishing Communication and Dissemination (C&D) materials, including website content**, was established (in the Consortium Guidance Note of the PCD/ D6.1).

Under this process, the text was reviewed by the coordinator (IRD). After that, it was presented to the General Assembly (GA) members for approval, where they evaluated it for scientific accuracy and confidentiality. The text received final approval and was finally professionally proofread in April 2024 (M4).

A more extensive text is considered for the second release of the website.

2.4. Graphic and development work

The Work Package 6 (WP6) leader, ICONS, benefits from an in-house team of experts, including a graphic designer and a developer. Together with the communication officer, they collaborate on the website's development and subsequent releases. The ICONS team strives to ensure that the website's visual elements and content accurately reflect the project's needs. Moreover, the team is focused on ensuring that the website (both the current landing page and future release) is developed according to user-experience design principles to facilitate the navigation of users and enable key stakeholders to find out the contents that are most valuable to them.

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The current landing page is designed to provide easy access to essential project information. This webpage contains:

- Visuals and images coherent with the project's visual identity
- Descriptive texts about the project
 - o *Its context*
 - o *Novelty*
 - o *Impact*
 - o *Market potential*
 - o *Consortium*
- Contacts
- Link to the first PR
- Links to the social media accounts

Once the graphic designer provided the developer with the necessary assets, the structure for the landing page was ready to host the final approved text by M3. The content followed, after the final approval detailed in the section above.

2.5. Views

As of June 2024, the landing page has received a total of **350 pageviews**. The distribution of the visits on a global scale is detailed in the map below. The impacts of the website will be continuously monitored and assessed throughout the duration of the project, as described in chapter 4 of the D6.1.

Figure 4: Visits by country (June 2024)

3. Second release

While the landing page is currently the main project’s entry point, as of M6, further developments are in the pipeline to ensure the Website is set to communicate and disseminate future results of the project.

The second release will present a more ‘structured’ interface, capable of hosting further information. It will be used for the following purposes:

- Share materials produced by FLAVIVACCINE, including public deliverables and scientific publications.
- Inform about Flaviviruses.
- Provide easy access to public D&C materials.
- Publish news about (or relevant to) the project.
- Cross-link it with external platforms, relevant initiatives, sister projects.
- Promote relevant events, webinars, workshops and other stakeholder engagement activities.

The sections of the website already decided and now work in motion to deliver this upgrade by August 2024 (M8).

3.1. The Web Map

A map was created and shared with the coordinator to agree on relevant sections to be included on the website. At M5, the ICONS team refined the map, reorganizing possible web pages to encourage navigation across sections and topics.

FLAVIVACCINE
Website tree map
v1.0 - May 2024

Figure 5: Web Map

The sections foreseen are:

- A. **Homepage:** as the first page available to the user, it contains the introduction and project video (when available). In the homepage, all links to the main sections are easily accessible. A menu leads the user to points B, C, D, and E listed below.
- B. **About:** this menu item contains pertinent information to understand the project. It opens a drop-down menu leading to further information on:
 - a. **Project:** presents an overview of FLAVIVACCINE, its context, and its impact.
 - b. **Market:** provides information on the project's market potential.
 - c. **Partners:** introduces the project consortium, including logo and contact information.
- C. **Flaviviruses:** this menu item opens a drop-down menu with:
 - a. **Intro:** describes the flavivirus.
 - b. **Dengue:** provides details on the virus.
 - c. **Yellow fever:** provides details on the virus.
 - d. **Zika:** provides details on the virus.
 - e. **West Nile:** provides details on the virus.
 - f. **Japanese encephalitis:** provides details on the virus.
- D. **Solution:** this menu items leads the user to information regarding the solution developed by the project to contrast the rising threats described in section C.
- E. **Knowledge:** this menu item opens a drop-down menu with:
 - a. **News and events** for the user to stay updated on the project's activities.
 - b. **Resources** to access documents, Media Kit, and public deliverables (can be filtered by categories).
 - c. **Job vacancies** related to the project activities, mostly PhD positions.

3.2. Timeline and next steps

Towards the successful completion of the website, a few more activities need to be completed.

Table 2: Upcoming production activities with description

Activities	Description	Process	Timing
Approval of text	Drafted by ICONS, the content shared on the website aims to attract the stakeholders' attention and increase their awareness, acceptance, and uptake of FLAVIVACCINE.	Subject to IRD and GA members' review.	By M6

<p>Graphic</p>	<p>While waiting for the final text, the graphic designer will work on the draft as a placeholder.</p>	<p>ICONS in-house process.</p>	<p>M6-M7</p>
<p>Development</p>	<p>Once received the graphic elements development can start to elevate the landing page to the final version of the website.</p>		<p>M7-M8</p>

As already mentioned, the website is structured to encourage navigation across sections and topics. The pages will be **regularly updated** during the project. All the content published on the website will be accessible to all viewers with no restrictions.

Conclusions

The FLAVIVACCINE website is a pivotal element of the project's C&D strategy, serving as the primary channel to engage key stakeholders across the vaccine value chain.

By offering clear and accessible information about the project's goals, impact, and innovations, the website aims to maximize visibility and support for FLAVIVACCINE. It ensures public access to essential updates, news, and deliverables, fostering transparency and engagement.

This deliverable (D6.5) completes the Plan for Communication and Dissemination (PCD - D6.1) as it outlines the development process of the website, detailing its structure and the steps taken to ensure its effectiveness. With the website's initial release in April 2024 and plans for a more comprehensive second release, the project is well-positioned to communicate its progress and achievements. Regular updates and maintenance will ensure the website remains a valuable resource throughout the project's lifecycle.

